

Massariosphaeria websteri sp. nov. and several members of the *Pleosporales* noteworthy to Pakistan

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Received 1 March 2010 / Accepted 30 June 2010

Abstract. A new species, *Massariosphaeria websteri*, on submerged decaying culms of a grass (possibly *Phragmites karka*) in freshwater in Pakistan is described, illustrated and compared with closely related taxa in the genus *Massariosphaeria*. It is characterized by immersed, scattered, subglobose to conical, ostiolate ascomata each with a papillate beak; 20–32 µm thick, 5–7 layers, polygonal to rectangular peridial cells; branched and anastomosed pseudoparaphyses; relatively large (170–245 × 26.5–35 µm), fissitunicate, cylindrical asci; and ascospores large-sized (av. 52.2 × 13.5 µm), narrowly fusiform to clavate, (7–) 8–11-septate, surrounded by a gelatinous sheath. Additionally, six other members of the *Pleosporales*, *Massariosphaeria typhicola*, *Lophiostoma caulium*, *Lophiostoma compressum*, *Lophiostoma quadrinucleatum*, *Nodulosphaeria aquilana*, and *Trichometasphaeria culmifida*, are reported.

Key words: aquatic fungi, *Dothideomycetidae*, freshwater ascomycetes, *Pleosporales*, taxonomy

Introduction

The present paper is based on the collection made by one of us (SHI) mostly from hilly areas of Pakistan. A number of species of *Pleospora* described earlier (Lucas & Iqbal 1969) formed a part of the present SHI Herbarium. In this paper, a new species, *Massariosphaeria websteri*, and six other members of the *Pleosporales* (*Dothideomycetes*) noteworthy to Pakistan are described and illustrated.

Materials and methods

The methods for microscopic work given in Tanaka & Harada (2003) have been followed. For ascospore septum position, the decimal system (Shoemaker 1984; Raja *et al.* 2008) was used. Holotype and isotype specimens were deposited in the SHI mycological reference collection, Department of Botany, University of the Punjab, Quid-e-Azam Campus, Lahore, Pakistan, and the fungal reference collection of HHUF (Hirosaki University).

Taxonomy

Massariosphaeria websteri Kaz. Tanaka & Iqbal, sp. nov.

Figs 1–14

Mycobank # MB 518620

Ascomata 300–350 µm alta, 370–570 µm diam., immersa, dispersa, subglobosa vel conica. Rostrum 50–70 µm longum, 90–110 µm latum, ostiolatum, papillatum vel absens. Paries ascomatis 20–32 µm crassus, ex cellulis 5–7 stratis rectangulatis vel polygonis compositus. Pseudoparaphyses ramificantes, anastomosantes. Asci 170–245 × 26.5–35 µm, fissitunicati, cylindrici, octospori. Ascosporae (41–) 46–60 (–66.5) × 11.5–16 µm, L/W (3.2–) 3.4–4.5 (–4.8), anguste fusiformes vel claviformes, (7–) 8–11-septatae, quaeque cum vagina gelatinosa obtectae.

Ascomata 300–350 µm high, 370–570 µm diam., immersed, scattered, subglobose to conical in longitudinal section, ostiolate. Beak 50–70 µm high, 90–110 µm wide, central, papillate, sometimes lacking. Ascomatal wall at side 20–32 µm thick, composed of 5–7 layers of polygonal cells 8.5–17.5 × 3–5 µm; wall around beak composed of rectangular to polygonal cells 5–7.5 µm diam.; inner wall around base

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Fig. 1. Line drawings of *Massariosphaeria websteri*. **a.** Ascospores. Bar = 10 µm. **b.** Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 1 mm. **c.** Longitudinal section of ascoma. Bar = 100 µm. All from the holotype (SHI 2007-FW1237)

composed of hyaline depressed cells. Pseudoparaphyses numerous, tortuous, 1.5–2 µm wide, branched, anastomosed. **Asci** 170–245 × 26.5–35 µm, fissitunicate, cylindrical, rounded at the apex, with an ocular chamber, stalked (13–25 µm long), with 8 ascospores biseriata above and uniseriate below. **Ascospores** (41–) 46–60 (–66.5) × 11.5–16 µm (av. 52.2 × 13.5 µm, $n = 90$), L/W (3.2–) 3.4–4.5 (–4.8) (av. 3.9, $n = 90$), narrowly fusiform to clavate, slightly curved, with a supramedian primary septum (0.40–0.48; av. 0.43,

$n = 90$), (7–) 8–11-septate (the number of septa in upper hemisphere + the primary septum + the number of septa in lower hemisphere = mostly 3+1+5, sometimes 3+1+4, 3+1+6, 4+1+5, 4+1+6), sometimes with a longitudinal septum, strongly constricted at the primary septum, less so at the others, the fourth or fifth cell from the apex enlarged, yellow to brown, finely echinulate, surrounded by a gelatinous sheath of 2–8 µm thick.

Figs 2–14. *Massariosphaeria websteri*. 2–6. Ascospores. Bars = 10 µm. 7. Ascospores with sheath (in India ink). Bar = 20 µm. 8. Pseudoparaphyses. Bar = 10 µm. 9–10. Asci. Bars = 20 µm. 11. Ascus apex with an ocular chamber. Bar = 10 µm. 12. Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 500 µm. 13. Ascoma in longitudinal section. Bar = 50 µm. 14. Ascomal wall. Bar = 10 µm. All from the holotype (SHI 2007-FW1237)

Type specimens (designated here): PAKISTAN, Dadar, 15 Jul 1975, on submerged decaying culms of a grass (possibly *Phragmites karka* (Retz.) Trin. ex Steud.), SHI 2007-FW1237, SHI mycological reference collection, Department of Botany, University of the Punjab, Quid-e-Azam Campus, Lahore, Pakistan (**holotype**), HHUF 30005 (**isotype**).

Etymology: named in honor of Dr. John Webster for his outstanding work on loculoascomycetous fungi.

Notes. This new species, *Massariosphaeria websteri*, is most similar to *M. typhicola* (P. Karst.) Leuchtm. in overall morphology and freshwater habitat. However, *M. websteri* can be separated from the latter by its large-sized asci and ascospores. In *M. websteri*, the asci are considerably longer and wider (170–245 × 26.5–35 µm) when compared with those of *M. typhicola* recorded to date (up to 170 × 27.5 µm; Table 1). The mean ascospore size of *M. websteri* is 52.2 × 13.5 µm, whereas those of *M. typhicola* are at maximum 53 × 13 µm (Table 1). Furthermore, longitudinal septa of ascospores, a character never reported for *M. typhicola*, might also be distinctive for *M. websteri*.

The name *Massariosphaeria* was first used for a section of *Leptosphaeria* Ces. & De Not. (Müller 1950), and later elevated to generic rank (Crivelli 1983). *Massariosphaeria* has been characterized by large transversely septate ascospores, which are thick-walled, and surrounded by a prominent gelatinous sheath (Tanaka & Harada 2004), and *ca* 21 species reported from terrestrial herbaceous plants (Leuchtmann 1985; Shoemaker & Babcock 1989) or aquatic habitats (Tanaka *et al.* 2005; Spooen 2007) have been accepted in this genus (Tanaka & Harada 2004). However, the generic concept of *Massariosphaeria* as currently used is problematic because several species allocated to this genus do not form a monophyletic group according to recent molecular phylogenetic study of the genus based on ribosomal DNA and RPB2 gene analyses (Wang *et al.* 2007). There is a possibility that *M. websteri* does not belong to *Massariosphaeria*, because it is similar to *M. typhicola*, a species which deviates from the type lineage (Wang *et al.* 2007), rather than to the type species of this genus (*M. phaeospora* (E. Müll.) Crivelli). We hope additional specimens and cultural isolates of *M. websteri* may be obtained to confirm the validity of generic placement of this species based on molecular sequence analysis.

Table 1. Comparison of *Massariosphaeria websteri* and *M. typhicola*

Taxa	Asci (µm)	Ascospores (µm)	No. of ascospore septum	Notes*	References **
<i>M. websteri</i>	170-245 × 26.5-35	(41-) 46-60 (-66.5) × 11.5-16	(7-) 8-11	-	19
<i>M. typhicola</i>	NA	38-52 × 8-10	9	4	7
	90-110 × 15-16	28-34 × 6-7	6-8	3	8
	NA	42-52 × 9-10	7	2	9
	NA	40-52 × 10-13	9	4	10
	120-140 × 19-24	40-48 × 10-12	9	4	10
	125-170 × 19-24	42-50 × 11-13	9	4	10
	130-160 × 19-21	40-50 × 10-12	9	4	10
	120-140 × 19-22	40-49 × 11-12	9	4	10
	140-160 × 18-20	37-53 × 8-11	8-10	6	11
	100-160 × 15-25	26-52 × 6-11	6-10	5	12
	120-140 × 19-24	40-48 × 10-12	9-10	4	13
	63-73 × 24-27.5	26.5-31.5 × 7.5-9	5-7	5	14
	(67-) 90-135 × 15-18	25-39 × 7-10.5	3-7-9	1	15
	80-100 × 10-14	27-32 × 5-7	7-8 (-9)	5	16
	(93-) 113-133 × 11.5-18	32-36 × 6-8	5-7 (-10)	1	17
	(80-) 82.5-115 (-157) × 14-19 (-21)	(30.5-) 32-43 (-49) × 6.5-10.5 (-12.5)	(6-) 7-8 (-10)	5	18
	130 × 21	36-51 (-53) × 9-10.5	7-9	5	19

* Recorded as: 1 = *Chaetomastia typhicola*, 2 = *Leptosphaeria baldingeriae*, 3 = *Leptosphaeria cladii*, 4 = *Leptosphaeria typhicola*, 5 = *Massariosphaeria typhicola*, 6 = *Phaeosphaeria typhicola*

** References: 7 = Saccardo (1883), 8 = Müller (1950), 9 = Holm (1952), 10 = Lucas & Webster (1967), 11 = Hedjaroude (1969), 12 = Leuchtmann (1985), 13 = Sivanesan (1984), 14 = Ridley (1988), 15 = Barr (1989), 16 = Shoemaker & Babcock (1989), 17 = Fallah & Shearer (2001), 18 = Tanaka & Harada (2004), 19 = this study

Figs 15–21. *Massariosphaeria typhicola*. 15–17. Ascospores. Bars = 10 μm . 18. Asci. Bar = 20 μm . 19. Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 500 μm . 20. Ascoma in longitudinal section. Bar = 50 μm . 21. Ascomal wall. Bar = 20 μm . All from SHI 2007-FW240

Massariosphaeria typhicola (P. Karst.) Leuchtm., Sydowia 37: 168, 1984.

Figs 15–21

Basionym: *Leptosphaeria typhicola* P. Karst., Bidr. Känn. Finl. Nat. Folk 23: 100, 1873.

Ascomata 190–250 μm high, 210–300 μm diam., erumpent to almost superficial, scattered, globose. Beak papillate, composed of dark brown thick-walled cells, ostiolate. Ascomatal wall 12–18 μm thick, composed of 3–5 layers of pale brown, polygonal cells of 3.5–14 \times 2.5–7.5 μm . Pseudoparaphyses cellular, numerous, septate, branched. **Asci** ca 130 \times 21 μm , fissionic, clavate, stipitate, 8-spored. **Ascospores** 36–51 (–53) \times 9–10.5 μm (av. 44.6 \times 9.7 μm , $n = 20$), L/W 4.1–5.0 (av. 4.6, $n = 20$), clavate to narrowly fusiform, 7–9-septate (2+1+4, 3+1+4, 3+1+5), with a primary septum suprmedian (0.37–0.45; av. 0.41, $n = 20$), brown, echinulate, with an entire gelatinous sheath.

Specimen examined: PAKISTAN, Saif-ul-Malook, 27 Aug 1964, on submerged decaying branches, SHI 2007-FW240.

Notes. This species has been considered as a cosmopolitan species occurring on various herbaceous and woody plants in terrestrial environments (Lucas & Webster 1967; Barr 1989; Shoemaker & Babcock 1989), as well as aquat-

Figs 22–28. *Lophiostoma caulium*. 22. Ascospore. Bar = 10 μm . 23–25. Asci. Bars = 20 μm . 26. Ascomal wall. Bar = 20 μm . 27. Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 500 μm . 28. Ascoma in longitudinal section. Bar = 100 μm . 22 from SHI 2007-302; 23 from SHI 2007-1720; 24, 26–28 from SHI 656A; 25 from SHI 656E

ic (Fallah & Shearer 2001; Shearer 2001) and marine (de Souza 1983) habitats. However, remarkable morphological variations, particularly in the size and septal number of ascospores have been reported for *M. typhicola* (Table 1). This might suggest that *M. typhicola* as reported to date is not a single species. Recent phylogenetic study on the freshwater ascomycete, *Massarina ingoldiana*, revealed that this species has evolved convergently in freshwater environment and the taxon can be divided into more than 3 species based on the phylogenetic tree as well as minute morphological differences in ascospores (Hirayama *et al.* 2010). Therefore, a reassessment of the species monophyly of *M. typhicola* should also be conducted.

Lophiostoma caulium (Fr.) Ces. & De Not., Schem. di Classif. Sferiacei: 45, 1863.

Figs 22–28

Basionym: *Sphaeria caulium* Fr., Syst. Mycol. (Lundae) 2(2): 509, 1823.

Ascomata 420–600 μm high, 500–750 μm diam., erumpent, scattered to gregarious, globose to subglobose, with a compressed beak. Beak composed of dark brown to black, thick-walled, globose cells of 2.5 μm diam., with a slit-like ostiole. Ascomatal wall 17–60 μm thick, composed of 5–11 layers of rectangular to polygonal cells of 5–18 \times 2.5–5 μm , with numerous brown hyphae around side of ascomata. Pseudoparaphyses trabecular, branched, anastomosed, with

Figs 29–34. *Lophiostoma compressum*. 29–31. Ascospores. Bars = 10 μm . 32. Ascus and pseudoparaphyses. Bar = 20 μm . 33. Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 500 μm . 34. Ascoma in longitudinal section. Bar = 100 μm . All from SHI 2007-641A

slime coating. **Asci** 100–130 \times 12–13 μm , fissitunicate, clavate, 8-spored. **Ascospores** 26–34 \times 6–8 μm , cylindrical with rounded ends, mostly 5-septate, yellowish-brown, with appendage-like sheath elongated at both ends.

Specimens examined: **PAKISTAN**, Baragali Murree, 20 May 1965, on dead branches of *Plectranthus rugosus* Wall., SHI 2007-302; Kalam, Swat, 27 Jul 1966, on dead branches of *P. rugosus*, SHI 2007-656A, SHI 2007-656E; Nathiagali, Murree, 30 Mar 1967, on dead branches of *P. rugosus*, SHI 2007-1720.

Notes. Many authors have considered that *L. caulium* to be a complex of several species with similar morphology (Chesters & Bell 1970; Holm & Holm 1988; Yuan & Zhao 1994; Tanaka & Harada 2003), but subdivision of this broadly defined species has not yet been made. Holm & Holm (1988) recognized five unnamed “varieties” mainly based on ascospore size and septation, and indicated them by letters as “var. a” to “var. e”. All of above materials examined in our study are similar to *L. caulium* “var. a” *sensu* Holm & Holm (1988).

Lophiostoma compressum (Pers.) Ces. & De Not., *Comm. Soc. crittog. Ital.* 1(1): 19, 1863. **Figs 29–34**

Basionym: *Sphaeria compressa* Pers., *Syn. Meth. Fung.* (Göttingen) 1: 56, 1801.

Ascomata 750–850 μm high, 900–1100 μm diam., almost immersed, erumpent at the beak, scattered to 2–3 gregarious, globose to subglobose, with a compressed beak. Beak *ca* 170–220 μm high, with a slit-like ostiole, composed of dark

brown, globose to rectangular, thick-walled cells 2.5 μm diam. Ascomatal wall 12.5–30 μm thick, at sides composed of 5–7 layers of flattened rectangular cells of 2.5 μm thick, at the base composed of subglobose to polygonal cells, 2.5–5 \times 2–3 μm . Pseudoparaphyses trabecular, branched, anastomosed, with a slimy coat. **Asci** 140–155 \times 15–16.5 μm , fissitunicate, clavate, (6–) 8-spored. **Ascospores** 18–28 \times 8–11 μm , cylindrical with rounded ends, with (3–) 5–7 transverse septa and 1 longitudinal septum, brown, without sheath.

Specimen examined: **PAKISTAN**, Kund, Kaghan, 18 Aug 1964, on dead branches of *Indigofera gerardiana* Graham, SHI 2007-641A.

Notes. This taxon is known as the type species of the genus *Platystomum* Trevis. The overall morphology of *Platystomum* is similar to that of *Lophiostoma* Ces. & De Not., but it has been treated as a distinct genus based on pseudoparaphyses type and ascospore septation (i.e. trabecular and dictyosporous in *Platystomum* vs. cellular and phragmosporous in *Lophiostoma*). Barr (1990, 1992) classified these two genera in the *Platystomaceae* (*Melanommatales*) and *Lophiostomataceae* (*Pleosporales*), respectively, and her classification has been followed by several authors (e.g. Abdel-Wahab & Jones 2000; Tanaka & Harada 2003). However, recent molecular study of these genera on the basis of 18S, 28S ribosomal DNA and RPB2 sequences suggests that they are congeneric (Zhang *et al.* 2009).

Lophiostoma quadrinucleatum P. Karst., *Bidr. Känn. Finl. Nat. Folk* 23: 85, 1873. **Figs 35–43**

Ascomata 320–340 μm high, 330–450 μm diam., erumpent, scattered, almost globose, with a compressed beak. Beak composed of dark brown, thick-walled, globose to rectangular cells of 2.5–5 μm diam., with a slit-like ostiole. Ascomatal wall 25–35 μm thick, composed of 7–9 layers of rectangular cells, 5–15 \times 3–7.5 μm , with numerous brown hyphae, 2.5–3.5 μm wide around the ascomatal side. Pseudoparaphyses trabecular, branched, anastomosed, with a slimy coat. **Asci** 115–145 \times 13–18 μm , fissitunicate, clavate, with a stipe 15–35 μm long, 8-spored. **Ascospores** 21–26 (–28) \times 7–9 μm (av. 23.7 \times 8.2 μm , $n = 30$), L/W 2.5–3.2 (av. 2.9, $n = 30$), broadly fusiform with somewhat rounded ends, 3-septate, with a primary septum usually submedian (0.50–0.54; av. 0.51, $n = 30$), brown, without sheath.

Specimen examined: **PAKISTAN**, Ziarat, 21 Apr 1984, on dead branches, SHI 2007-1003.

Notes. This specimen fits well within the genus *Lophiostoma*, and agrees in most respects with the description of *L. quadrinucleatum* provided by Chesters & Bell (1970) and Holm & Holm (1988).

Nodulosphaeria aquilana (D. Sacc.) L. Holm, *Symb. Bot. Upsal.* 14(3): 83, 1957. **Figs 44–52**

Basionym: *Leptosphaeria aquilana* D. Sacc., *Syll. Fung.* (Abellini) 17: 724, 1905.

Ascomata 190–280 μm high, 260–350 μm diam., immersed, erumpent at the top, scattered, globose to subglo-

Figs 35–43. *Lophiostoma quadrinuclatum*. 35–37. Ascospores. Bars = 10 μ m. 38. Pseudoparaphyses. Bar = 20 μ m. 39. Ascumata on host surface. Bar = 500 μ m. 40–41. Asci. Bars = 20 μ m. 42. Ascum in longitudinal section. Bar = 100 μ m. 43. Ascomal wall. Bar = 20 μ m. All from SHI 2007-1003

bose. Beak 50–65 μ m high, 70–100 μ m wide, papillate, ostiolate, composed of globose slightly thick-walled cells of 2.5–5 μ m diam., with numerous setae. Setae 12–25 μ m long, ca. 5 μ m thick at the base, black to dark brown, thick-walled. Ascumatal wall uniformly 17.5–25 μ m thick, composed of 4–5 layers of polygonal cells (10–18 \times 2.7–7 μ m), with brown septate hyphae 3–4 μ m wide at the side. Pseudoparaphyses cellular, septate, branched. Asci 95–120 \times 14–17 μ m, fissitunicate, cylindrical, with a short stipe of ca 10 μ m long or almost sessile, 8-spored. Ascospores 42–52 \times 5–6.5 μ m (av. 45.4 \times 5.8 μ m, n = 40), L/W 7.2–8.7 (av. 7.9, n = 40), fusi-form, 4 (–5)-septate (mostly 1+1+2, rarely 2+1+2), with a primary septum supramedian (0.37–0.43; av. 0.40, n = 40), pale yellow, with globose or conical appendage of 3–4 μ m diam. at the both ends.

Specimen examined: PAKISTAN, Saif-ul-Malook, Sept 1966, on dead stems of *Swertia petiolata* Royle, SHI 2007-544a.

Notes. Above mentioned specimen matches very well to the descriptions of *N. aquilana* (Holm 1957; Lucas & Webster

Figs 44–52. *Nodulosphaeria aquilana*. 44–46. Ascospores. Bars = 10 μ m. 47–48. Asci. Bars = 20 μ m. 49. Ascumata on host surface. Bar = 200 μ m. 50. Pseudoparaphyses. Bar = 10 μ m. 51. Ascum in longitudinal section. Bar = 50 μ m. 52. Setae at ascomal apex. Bar = 20 μ m. All from SHI 2007-544a

1967; Shoemaker 1984) in the size of asci and ascospores, but most ascospores were 4-septate. Lucas & Webster (1967) noted that ascospores of *N. aquilana* are predominantly 5- and occasionally 4-septate.

Trichometasphaeria culmifida (P. Karst.) L. Holm, Symb. Bot. Upsal. 14(3): 140, 1957. **Figs 53–61**

Basionym: *Leptosphaeria culmifida* P. Karst., Bidr. Känn. Finl. Nat. Folk 23: 103, 1873.

Ascumata 110–180 μ m high, 110–240 μ m diam., almost immersed, erumpent at the top, scattered, globose. Beak papillate, ostiolate, with numerous setae. Setae black to dark brown, one-celled, 25–35 μ m long, 2.5–3 μ m wide at the base, thick-walled. Ascumatal wall 5–10 μ m thick, composed of 3–4 layers of rectangular, thin-walled, flattened cells (1.5–2.5 μ m thick). Pseudoparaphyses cellular, 1.5–3 μ m wide, septate, branched. Asci 78–95 \times 10–12 μ m (av. 88.7 \times 10.7 μ m, n = 20), fissitunicate, cylindrical, with a short stipe of 3–8 μ m long, 8-spored. Ascospores 18–23 \times 4.5–6 μ m (av. 20.5 \times 5.2 μ m, n = 30), L/W 3.6–4.4 (av. 4.0, n = 30), fusi-

Figs 53–61. *Trichometasphaeria culmifida*. 53–56. Ascospores. Bars = 10 μm . 57. Pseudoparaphyses. Bar = 10 μm . 58. Asci. Bar = 20 μm . 59. Ascomata on host surface. Bar = 500 μm . 60. Ascoma in longitudinal section. Bar = 20 μm . 61. Ascomal wall. Bar = 20 μm . All from SHI 2007-1004

form, 3-septate, with a primary septum mostly submedian (0.49–0.54; av. 0.51, $n = 30$), pale yellow, with an entire gelatinous sheath.

Specimen examined: PAKISTAN, Lahore, 10 Oct 1974, on dead leaves of *Typha angustifolia* L., SHI 2007-1004.

Notes. *Trichometasphaeria culmifida* appears to have a worldwide distribution on various monocotyledons. There are many records of this species from Europe (e.g. Holm 1957; Munk 1957; Dennis 1978; Eriksson 1992; Scheuer & Chlebicki 1997), North America (Barr 1992), and Asia (Otani & Mikawa 1971) including Pakistan (Ahmad 1978). Ahmad (1978) has reported this species on culms of *Saccharum spontaneum* and on peelings of *Triticum aestivum*.

Acknowledgements. S.H. Iqbal is highly grateful to Prof. Rass Masood to provide working place inside the herbarium with permission to work till late hours at night. This study was partially supported by Hirotsuki University Grant for Exploratory Research by Young Scientists.

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